

NUTRI•KNOW

Farmer's
Encyclopedia
on innovative
Nutrient
Management
Solutions

EIP-AGRI
Operational Group
Duncannon Blue Flag Farming

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming and Communities Scheme: Sustainably Restoring, Protecting and Enhancing Water Quality

Activities

- Create a farm-specific Pollution Potential Zone (PPZ) plan for each farm.
- Provide farmers with a full-time Sustainability Manager to help participating farmers achieve the project objectives by guiding them through their PPZ plans and by developing and delivering several knowledge exchange initiatives.
- Monitor farm practice change and water quality in the wider catchment area.
- Develop community-wide engagement to create a sense of local ownership and responsibility for the local rivers.

Further details

Total budget: € 721.197,00

Total financed: € 550.000,00

Main funding source: Rural development 2014-2020 for Operational Groups

Rural Development Programme:

2014IE06RDNP001 - Ireland

Rural Development Programme

(Regional)

Ended, 2018-2023

Wexford County, Ireland

**Wexford County Council
Environment Section**

Project coordinator

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<https://www.facebook.com/duncannonblueflagfip/>

Objectives

- To contribute to the recovery of the Blue Flag status at Duncannon Beach, Co. Wexford.
- Sustainably restore, protect and enhance the quality of the bathing and riverine waters at Duncannon by reducing pollution from rural agricultural and domestic sources whilst also protecting farm incomes.
- Develop an effective model for future sustainable management of similar catchments.
- Foster positive relations between the farmers and householders in the catchment area and the local natural landscape, particularly the water environment and associated biodiversity.

Implementing water quality improvement works by fencing off access to rivers, inclusion of riparian zones and implementing sediment traps

Results

- Bacterial, chemical and ecological quality of the two coastal streams at Duncannon Beach improved.
- Bathing water quality at Duncannon Beach improved.
- Participants gained a greater sense of local ownership, responsibility and appreciation for the local water environment.
- Farm-specific PPZ maps were developed and were used as education and engagement tools to show farmers in a simple visual way, the water-quality risks specific to their farms.
- A range of innovative and cost-effective farm management practices for water-quality protection was demonstrated.
- Effective communication and sharing of local water-quality results with the local community.
- Local citizen scientist groups were established by local community members to monitor local stream quality and develop a pollution alert system.

Context

Elevated bacteria levels in bathing water quality at Duncannon Beach together with the loss of its Blue Flag status of environmental excellence in 2007 had a major impact on tourism in the area. Overall, 35 farmers covering a catchment area over 975 hectares, came together to contribute to the recovery of the Blue Flag status.

Location in the Nutri-Know value chain

Sustainably
Restoring,
Protecting and
Enhancing Water
Quality

With guidance from a dedicated sustainability manager, farmers developed a results-based rewards scheme to assess the pollution risks on farms and formed Pollution Potential Zone (PPZ) maps. To improve their PPZ scores, participating farmers implemented water protection improvement works on their farms and the catchment area. Overall, 15.5km of watercourses were fenced off, water troughs were moved 20m from waterways and sediment traps were installed to trap and filter run-off. At a farm level, the catchment farms became more efficient, the number of septic tank failures reduced and compliance above the Nitrates Directives was observed. At a local level, a reduction in bacterial pollution at Duncannon Beach was recorded and an improvement in ecological quality was observed. At a community level, the participants reported a sense of ownership and appreciation for the local water environment.

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